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HOW MANY MANAGED HONEY BEE COLONIES
IN A SEMIARID ISLAND? THE CASE STUDY OF LAMPEDUSA

*Quante colonie di Apis mellifera in un'isola semiarida?
Il caso studio di Lampedusa*

Lampedusa (35°30'05"N - 12°36'34"E), 20,2 km², is part of Pelagic Archipelago, located in the Mediterranean Sea. The mean annual rainfall is 300 mm with extremely irregular (October-March) rain events. Mean annual temperature is 19 °C. The whole island was subject to intense degradation due to human colonisation, causing during the last century a severe depletion of animal and plant species. Lampedusa Municipality is associated beneficiary in the Project LIFE16CCA/IT/000011 "DESERT ADAPT – Preparing desertification areas for increased climate change, aimed at analysing key issues related to the state of ecosystems in Mediterranean areas under desertification risk, state and values of the ecosystem services and options for sustainable managements and conservation.

Within the Lampedusa DAM (Desert Adaptation Model), beekeeping has been identified as a possible model of sustainable management in this Mediterranean island, and a preliminary report was aimed at detecting the honey bee colonies on the island, the assessment of wild bees species richness and a review of literature on the impact of honey bees on wild bee populations.

At present, 108 managed honey bee colonies of *Apis mellifera siciliana* are present in Lampedusa, settled in 2 apiaries (1 owner) within the municipality rules and managed following the Best Beekeeping Practices guidelines.

Currently, about 60 species of wild bees are reported, some of them recently found during the Project monitoring activity, (LO VERDE *et al.*, 2023). All the species present on the island are also reported for Sicily, and

none of them appears in the Red Lists of Italian and European Apoidea (NIETO *et al.*, 2014; RASMONT *et al.*, 2017; QUARANTA *et al.*, 2018). No data are available about their abundance and biology.

Despite more than 450 plant species have been reported in the island, among them several endemisms, blossom sources are strongly affected by semi-arid climate and by limited agricultural surfaces. In this context, also ornamental plants can represent a suitable food source.

Our knowledge on pollinator diversity and the threats in such insular conditions should be further improved, assessing the potential limiting resources for wild bee populations in the semiarid environments characterizing Lampedusa Island.

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